

The Relationship between Eco Design and Emotional Experiences

- A Case of Emotionally Rewarding Eco Friendly Bottled Water in Japan -

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Abstract: This paper deals with an emotional effect as a motivator for users to participate in recycling bottled water. Branding has become among critical success factors in the bottled water industry. Building on Desmet's (2003, 2007) classification of product emotions, we attempt to analyze ILOHAS, eco-friendly brand of bottled water in Japan. In explaining the emotional responses of consumers to Ilohas, the authors assert that interaction between aesthetic and social product emotions results in rich and complicated emotional experiences. Along with the social experiences that traditional eco-products offer, Ilohas provides richer experiences related to touch and sound. When the latter experience is positive and fun, these experiences are likely to offset the social responsibilities and duties being emphasized by the existing eco-products. The above emotional compensation may not fully explain the success of the eco-product, but does act as a strong motivator that is different from the extant methods of direct physical compensation and point rewards.

Key words: *eco design, recycling, compactable bottle, emotional design*

1. Introduction

To select, purchase and further use a product/service is generally what a person intends and often prefers. Some people enjoy shopping as addiction and experience flow when the product/service provides excellent usability/convenience and/or aesthetic value. Recycling is also involved in the life cycle of a product once it is at least partly consumed. After the brief excitement of opening the package, we are forced to dispense with the product in the recycling phase after its use. Consumers, when purchasing a certain product, gradually take into account the above experiences concerned with recycling.

Bottled water manufacturers are at least partly responsible for the collection of disposed bottles.[6] These manufacturers are thus trying hard to devise every possible technical solution to be more environment-friendly. Yet, companies thus far have not been very active in trying to increase the consumers' awareness of and voluntary participation in eco friendly consumption of the bottled water. One notable exception is ILOHAS, bottled water brand from Coca-Cola Japan launched in 2009. Ilohas is designed to twist the bottle with ease to a

minimal size. Consumers can have fun/playfulness due to sound and touch during the twisting process. Consumers are emotionally compensated to enjoy fun/playfulness during the process, as the twisting action itself is fun for the consumers [4, 7]. The technology is akin to the one in the existing compactable bottle. Yet the responses from consumers have been very complicated, either being generally exciting or interesting. This study applies Desmet and Hekkert (2007)'s framework of product experience to the specific case of Ilohas. This paper collected information from e-mail correspondences with Coca-Cola Japan and from secondary sources including three major daily newspapers and magazines. Focus group interviews (FGI) were conducted with Japanese designers and then Japanese consumers. The results of the secondary sources and FGI were analyzed based on the extant works of Desmet, Hekkert (2003, 2007) and Lilley (2006) [1, 2, 12].

2. Eco-friendly strategy of bottled water, eco-friendly bottle design

Bottled water is drinking water packaged in bottles for personal consumption. Bottled water is differentiated mainly by its composition and provenance of the source. The water also gained benefits from investments of manufacturers in branding in general and brand image in particular. Bottled water has long been criticized as eco-destructive due to its packaging of plastics that are not bio-gradable. Corporation-led sustainable design strategies thus include changes in the material of the bottle and reduction in its weight. Such a strategy is reflected in the reduce-maintenance-upgrade-reuse-recycle model [19]. Notable examples that follow the above trend include Coca-Cola's PlantBottle™ that partly uses plant-based materials (30%), new bottles of Danone for its brands Evian and Volvic that utilize r-PET to substantially reduce the weight of the bottle, and Pepsi's Eco-Fina Bottle™.

Another eco-friendly (recycle) model deals with the redesign of the bottle to be compactable to reduce the weight of the bottle that will increase the efficiency in the collection process. The above strategy is among the consumer-led models. In the above model, how to design consumer motivation is also critical to the success of the model [19]. Motivation has largely been devised from marketing viewpoint in the form of point mileage, discount coupons and priorities to limited editions. Re-source, a brand launched by Nestle in North America, is experimenting with the program of in-store recycling that networks local stores with non governmental organizations (NGOs) related to their environments. Under this system, once consumers bring the empty bottle to the local, they are awarded incentive points.

3. Emotionally rewarding Eco-Product

Aesthetic design such as artistic works on the package of the bottled water can instantly attract visceral responses such as 'I love this! I want it!' from the consumers. The design can play an emotional role that goes beyond its simplicity of containing water, functionality and efficiency [14]. Elements of emotional design concerned with the package of the bottled water means the aesthetic aspects to provide sensorial satisfaction.

Yet, these elements can also address social issues including water shortage. For instance, the 'Drink 1, Give 10' campaign by Volvic provides the psychological satisfaction of 'doing the right thing'. Y Water, bottled vitamin water for kids, is in the shape of the letter Y, so that empty bottles can be assembled to make a block toy like

Lego. These types of design are difficult to apply to mainstream bottled water brand, but can provide new motivational factors as a fun toy for play [11].

3-1. Classification of Product emotions

Product-human Interaction can be explained by examining the system in and around design. This interaction can be structured to include the consumer, the product as an object, the attributes of the product and the consumer's responses. Design that appeals to and extracts a user response can be investigated in the causality of the whole system. Response here refers to the emotional actions of the consumer when she or he first encounters the product as object. Elements of the response not just include image/impression-related reactions, including being balanced and beautiful, but also psychological ones related to being attractive [5, 8]. Design, thus physical, attributes of the product is classified as cognitive. This cognitive attribute is universal relative to the more subjective image/impression-related attributes. Brand and price of a product is regarded as a type of cognitive attribute that can either reinforce or distort the initial causality. This study deals with the product development and emotional aspect of design in general. In particular, this study is concerned with physical attributes of design and the consumers' emotional responses related to the use of the product in a limited sense. Use in the bottled water generally refers to drinking the water and bringing the package along until the consumers use up the content (water). "Use" in this paper is more broadly defined to include the emotional responses of the consumer even in the collection phase to provide diverse perspectives on the consumer emotions concerned with the use of bottled water.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) attempted to suggest a framework that includes all possible affective experiences involved in actual human-product interaction. The above interaction covers instrumental and non-instrumental interaction, and even non-physical interaction. The above experiences can be distinguished and separated into three distinct components or levels of product experiences including aesthetic experience, experiencing of meaning, and emotional experience. From the cognitive perspective of emotion, based on Frijda (1986), Desmet (2003) defines emotions related to a product as an appraisal process in which the individual appraises the product as (potentially) harming or favoring one or several of that person's concerns [1,5]. Emotional response is not just concerned with styling. It is more about affluent emotions that cover both pleasant and unpleasant emotions. Multiple emotions can be involved in the process [1,2]. These emotions include surprise, instrumental, aesthetic, social and interest.

Figure 1. Classification of Product Emotions [1]

3-2. Bottled Water market and regulatory environments in Japan

Figure 2. The Market Size and Share of the Bottled Water Market in Japan
(source: Asahi Daily, May 8, 2010)

The bottled water market in Japan registered remarkable growth from 2001 to 2007 due to the consumer trends concerning healthier life styles. With healthy revenue growth, the competition in the market was moderate. However, since the latter half of 2008, the market has not demonstrated growth at least partly due to global economic recession. The above slow market growth along with the low switching costs and high storage costs have recently intensified rivalry between and among major players in the Japanese market. The major players in the market include the market leaders Suntory and Kirin along with European leader Danone (Evian and Volvic) and the U.S. giants Coca-Cola and Pepsi-Cola. Major bottled water manufacturers needed to find ways to survive and further grow in the stagnated market. A majority of the manufacturers went for eco friendly bottle mainly in terms of material and the weight of the bottle. The recent trends in the light weight bottle include the bottle from Suntory (36g) and from Kirin (35g). The lightest bottle is Ilohas of 12g. Yet, Ilohas was more than just an eco friendly bottle. It integrates eco friendliness with emotion. Major cities in Japan request consumers to squeeze bottles in the process of waste disposal. The above regulatory environments in Japan also motivate bottled water manufacturers to develop squeezable bottles. The section below will analyze Ilohas from Desmet's three levels of product experiences [1, 2].

3-3. Product Emotions in the Bottled water

1) Aesthetic experiences

ILOHAS is a brand of bottled water that offers a concept of eco-friendliness. This product not just provides the concept of eco-friendliness but has the elements of playfulness as a motivator [11]. Within six months of its launch, over 200 million units were sold, and the product was ranked among the top thirty best selling items in 2009, a very rare case for an eco-product. In terms of package, a majority of bottled water brands in Japan, including the best selling brand 'Natural Water (*Tennensui*)' by Suntory, are featured with calligraphy using Chinese characters. Meanwhile, Ilohas provides a light and modern feel due to the utilization of Japanese alphabet *Hirakana*. As for Color, the main color of Ilohas is a bright green quite different from the blue color used for the package of many other bottled water brands.

The feel and touch of twisting the bottle after use gives a refreshing moment to users. Such a moment can lead to the addicted purchase of the brand (Fukao Norio, during an interview with Nikkei net). The light weight bottle, following strenuous efforts of the company to reduce its weight gives an insecure feel when users hold it. When users hold the bottle nearly full with water, the water can be spilled out at least a little. Some users do not feel comfortable about the insecurity of holding the bottle or the squeaky sound when squeezing the bottle. These emotions vary by individual.

Figure 3. Visual explanation about compactable bottle and Squeezable bottle

2) Experience of meaning

The brand name 'Ilohas' is an integration of traditional Japanese verse style '*iroha-uta* (iloha song)' and LOHAS to pursue health and environments. The name appears to be modern and trendy, but it also reflects traditional Japanese emotions. Therefore, even though it is a Coca-Cola product, it appeals to Japanese consumers who have long trusted and cherished Japanese products with a traditional Japanese identity. In the ads and on its home page, the company has offered specific information about the effects of Ilohas including the annual amount of PET reduced from the *shiboreru* (squeezable) bottle and the amount of CO₂ Emission. The company has consistently implemented an eco-promotion strategy, notably in the case of the Eco Art project.

Consumers exposed to this eco friendly branding strategy feel satisfied to meet the social pressures for environmental concerns.

Figure 4. An Ad that Publicizes the Sales of ILOHAS over 100 million bottles and the environmental effects of the sales amount.

Figure 5. Ilohas Eco Art Project by Mark Jenkins, 'Homeless Animals in the concrete Jungle', 2009.10

3) Emotional experience

Consumers feel the sensorial satisfaction of sound and touch when they squeeze the Ilohas bottle along with moral satisfaction [9]. Their satisfaction is greater when they realize the environmental contributions of their behavior. The company's slogan of 'Change the World just by the choice, drink, and squeeze' and the explanation in the bottle for 'Ecoru(eco), botoru(bottle), shiboru(squeeze)' place emphasis on Lohas(Lifestyles of Health and Sustainability) and are clearly related to the above squeezing behavior. The above message, when repeatedly exposed to consumers, can significantly reduce the uncomfortable responses from the customers aligned with eco-friendly messages. The message can instead reinforce the positive response of the consumers who react in affirmative manners to sound and the tactile touch of the squeezing behavior.

The three levels of product experiences described above can be categorized utilizing Desmet's five emotions of instrumental, social, surprise, interest and aesthetic [1].

Instrumental product emotions: There exist instrumental aims beyond fundamental/basic needs of quenching the thirst in the package of the bottle water, including play with the package. People feel satisfied and/or dissatisfied depending on what they want and need from the package.

Social product emotions: Consumers feel dissatisfied with the package of Ilohas when they firmly believe that a package of the bottled water must be secure enough to hold firmly to bring along with them. Meanwhile, if consumers believe that the package should be eco-friendly in design, the package of Ilohas is then satisfactory due to its easily squeezed material. Excessive squeezing to maximize the fun from the squeezing behavior appears to be destructive and/or violent. Yet, since the behavior will result in being socially responsible and produce eco-friendly outcomes, consumers feel satisfied in more complicated manners. Eco-products, notably in the case of the hybrid car, are largely regarded as having high development costs, costly price and inefficiency. Yet, as the price that Ilohas commands is approximate to that of general bottled water, consumers feel more with ease and satisfied.

Surprise product emotions: Consumers feel unpleasant when the content(water) overflows when they first grip the package. Yet, once accustomed to it, they find the experience of a fun to cater the multiple senses of the consumers.

Interest product emotions: In the context of Ilohas bottle, consumers can be attracted to the exceptional structure of the package that can be squeezed with ease.

Aesthetic product emotions: Consumers can react either positively or negatively to the physical appearances of the package. Yet, they can still have rich and beneficial experiences with a bottle that appeals to multiple senses of sight, sound, and touch [10].

Figure 6. ILOHAS: Aesthetic Product Emotions, Source: revised from Desmet (2003)

The emotions elicited from Ilohas are richer in comparison with those for the general eco-friendly bottled water. Ilohas appeals to the aesthetic emotions particularly through sound and touch. Ilohas also elicits surprising and interest product emotions due to its easily squeezable material and the unique sound during the *squeezing* process. These emotions help consumers to enjoy the fun. Responses from consumers have been expressed by

influencers including power bloggers on the internet. Some bloggers uploaded an article to describe how refreshed they felt after squeezing the package. Others uploaded a video file to YouTube to detail how to squeeze the bottle in different new ways. These new and unfamiliar experiences will inspire more creative ideas. The emotions concerned with social and aesthetic product emotions are not just complicated but paradoxical as well. *Squeezing* behavior appears to be violent at first glance, but it is a very effective way to relieve the insecurity and further provide stability. These complicated emotional responses, when integrated with the positive emotions of eco friendliness and sustainability, form unique and independent image of the brand.

Table 1. Emotions related to Eco Friendly Bottled Water Brands

Bottled Water Emotions	General Eco friendly Bottled Water Brand (Aquafina, DASANI, and Evian)	I LOHAS
instrumental	Activated (satisfaction)	Activated (satisfaction, relaxed)
social	Activated (admiration, satisfaction / dissatisfaction)	activated (admiration, satisfaction / dissatisfaction)
aesthetic	Calm (deferent, calm)	activated(admiration, joyfulness, desire / irritation, disgust)
interest	Calm (deferent, calm)	activated(inspiration, desire, love)
surprise	calm(deferent, calm)	activated (desire, love / alarm)

Source: Compiled by the authors based on secondary sources concerned with the bottled water brands

Between general eco-friendly brands and Ilohas, there appears to be little differences in instrumental and social emotions. In terms of quenching the thirst with healthier water, no significant differences can be observed in instrumental emotions. In view of eco-friendliness, both groups demonstrate little differences. Yet, in terms of aesthetic, interest and surprise emotions, both groups show differences. In view of interest emotions, the elements of playfulness in the process of twisting and twitting the bottle are unique in Ilohas. Such playfulness can elicit otherwise negative responses related to eco friendliness. Evian has since the late 1990s introduced the concept of compactable bottle, but the concept has never occupied the minds of the consumers who have long associated themselves with the pure and clean image of Evian. Ilohas has integrated the compactable concept with playfulness and was able to move the minds of the consumers.

4. Conclusion

When explaining the emotional responses of consumers to Ilohas, the authors assert that interaction between aesthetic and social product emotions results in rich and complicated emotional experiences. As Lilley (2009) has rightly put it, consumers are slow to adopt more sustainable behaviors [3,18]. Moreover, behavioral changes are often short lived [17]. Along with the social experiences that traditional eco-products offer, Ilohas provides richer experiences concerned with touch and sound. When the experiences are positive and fun and/or playful [11], the experiences are likely to offset the social responsibilities and duties being emphasized by the existing eco products. The above emotional compensation may not fully explain the success of the eco-product, but it can act as a strong motivator that is different from the extant methods of direct physical compensation and point rewards. Future research needs to focus at least partly on various psychological compensations in relation to eco products. When examining Ilohas, the authors were not able to reach a conclusion concerning the sensorial aspects of Ilohas. Emotions related to squeezing behavior can be addictive just like any other violent behaviors. The above behavior will simultaneously appeal to multiple senses in both positive and negative ways, particularly when it is linked to social emotions to products. Future research can address the above issues, notably for the differences and, further, sustainability of the above emotions in comparison with simple positive consumer emotions. Also, emotional responses to eco products differ by user group. Future research thus needs to investigate how eco-friendliness coupled with playfulness can attract emotional responses from different user groups.

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